

Christ Apostolic Church, Ori-Oke Aanun [sic] (Mountain of Mercy), Ojoo, Ibadan, Oyo State

also known as "Prayer Mountain in Ibadan, Oyo State"

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Prayer Mountains, also known as Ori-Oke (in Yoruba parlance), are centres of spiritual pilgrimage and within the praxis of Nigerian Christian lexicon, are synonymous with the enactment of a sacred space on a mountaintop characterized by various prayer regimes, rituals, exorcism and religious practices, aimed at eliciting the help of the divine to alleviate the existential challenges of devotees who visit these Prayer Mountains from different walks of life, are of the different sexes, and belong to different strata of socio-economic status. The prominent Ori-Oke (Prayer Mountains) of the South Western part of Nigeria are largely concentrated in the Oyo and Osun States of Nigeria. This entry examines one of the prominent Ori-Oke (Prayer Mountains) in Ibadan, Oyo State, which is the Christ Apostolic Church, Ori-Oke Aanun [sic] located in Ojoo area in Ibadan. The Yoruba word 'Aanu', being the correct spelling of word 'Aanun' as it is being used by the proprietors of the prayer mountain connotes mercy. It therefore suggests that the prayer mountain is a place where people obtain mercy and find solutions to their existential problems. It is one of the prominent Ori-Oke that are largely visited by people who desire solutions to their life crisis and those of their loved ones in Ibadan. Judging by the volume of human traffic that throng these prayer mountains and by the responses of people during a pilot survey in knowing the mostly accessed prayer mountains in the Southwest of Nigeria. The prominent Prayer Mountains in Ibadan are Ori-Oke Aanun, Ibadan; Ori-Oke Automatic, Ibadan; and Ori-Oke Olorunkole, Ibadan. The Ori-Oke Aanun (Mountain of Mercy), Ojoo, Ibadan was founded by Prophet Moses Aladeolu through God's leading. He was led by God's voice to a thick forest after many days of prayer and fasting and through prophetic utterances from his first host in Ibadan. He was a successful contractor to the Oyo State government but was compelled by God to find the unexplored mountain that has become a succour for many seeking divine intervention to their many existential problems. And today, the unexplored forest has become a community thriving with different spiritual, social and economic activities. People have given various reasons for visiting Prayer Mountains. Some of these include spiritual restoration, soul purification, re-awakening, revivals and healings. Incidentally, some are of the opinion that some problems may not be solved until a visit or more to the mountain is carried out. Some churches or prayer grounds who have no affinity with a prayer mountain might have named their place of gathering Ori-Oke because the term Ori-Oke is synonymous with a place for miracles. However, prayer sites with mountain topography are predominantly found in the South West which many attest to the mountains providing a secluded and serene environment for spiritual exercise. Many of those who visit the Prayer Mountains have often given their premise for attaching significance to the Prayer Mountains because Jesus Christ, during his earthly ministry, often visited or retreated to a mountaintop location to commune with God and even taught the crowd of people there at some instances with miracles being recorded. On the other hand too, some have visited some Prayer Mountains for the wrong reasons and became victims of fake prophets. Each Prayer Mountain has its own peculiarity. Hence, this entry looks at the appealing characteristics of Ori-Oke Aanun especially within the context of the prominent Prayer Mountains in Ibadan, Oyo State.

Date Range: 1900 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Ibadan, Oyo State

Region tags: Western Africa, Western Nigeria, Nigeria, Southwest Nigeria, Africa, Oyo state, Nigeria, Nigeria

Ibadan, Oyo State is the largest city in West Africa while Oyo State is one of the significant state in the Southwestern part of Nigeria and it is part of the Yorubaland that has been since the 18th century.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: i. Soede N. Yaovi Et Al. Eds. Ori-Oke Spirituality and Social Change in Africa: Contemporary Perspectives. Mankon Bamenda: Langaa Research & Publishing CIG, 2018.
- Source 2: ii. Aina, O. F. Psychotherapy by Environmental Manipulation and the Observed Symbolic Rites on Prayer Mountains in Nigeria. *Mental Health, Religion & Culture* 9, no. 1 (2006): 1-13.
- Source 3: iii. Ayoola, Olukayode K. & Ogunewu, Micheal A. A Critical Investigation into the Use of Prayer Mountains Among “Aladura” Christians of Southwestern, Nigeria. *HUMASS: McU Journal of Humanities, Management, Applied and Social Sciences* 3 (2020): 107-119.

Notes: These 3 print sources explain the phenomenon of Ori-Oke (Prayer Mountains) in Southwestern Nigeria, some of their practices and the doctrines that serve as the foundation for the identified practices, and the expressed perceptions of some of the people that visit these mountains for the resolution of their existential problems

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://independent.ng/prayer-mountains-centres-for-answered-prayers/>
- Source 1 Description: The article discusses the various reasons that those who visit prayer mountains have for visiting them
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.thenewman.org.ng/2021/09/list-of-ori-oke-prayer-mountains-in.html>
- Source 2 Description: This article is a compilation of a few prayer mountains in Nigeria. Some of them are very popular and widely known while others are not. It must be noted that going to a prayer mountain is not always a criterion for answered prayers.
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.lucipost.com/2019/03/the-story-of-the-most-popular-prayer-mountains-in-osun-state/>
- Source 3 Description: In this report, Lucy of the Osun Citizen presents the story of the three most popular out of these prayer mountains. Because of its significance, added to the list is a prayer ground

(not a mountain) where the popular Apostle Joseph Ayo Babalola received his calling

Notes: The authors of the write-ups in the online sources describe the ideological perception of the people who visit the Prayer Mountains and their varied experiences.

Reference: Abegunrin, Gbenga. "Nigeria: Ori-oke Anu Attracts All Sort". January 23, 2011. p.<https://allafrica.com/stories/201101241260.html>

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Notes: The Christ Apostolic Church Ori-Oke Aanun (Mountain of Mercy), Ojoo, Ibadan was reportedly discovered by the founder, Prophet Moses Aladeolu. The mountain was initially located in a thick forest with no previous human development in the adjoining environment until Prophet Moses Aladeolu supernaturally found the mountain area which led to the development of the adjoining area. It has now become a beehive of human activities today.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

– Tree, grove, or forest

– Other [specify]: Montaneous elevation

Notes: The Christ Apostolic Church Ori-Oke Aanun (Mountain of Mercy), Ojoo, Ibadan is an elevated mountainous and rocky area with a little open ground that has been cleared of initial vegetation

Type of elevation

– Mountain

Notes: The Christ Apostolic Church Ori-Oke Aanun (Mountain of Mercy), Ojoo, Ibadan is a very wide mountainous area with a relatively flat summit. It is surrounded by other smaller accompanying rocks.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Clearing

– Trackway or road-surface

– Plantings

Notes: This is only a current and contemporary reality. At the initial stage the Christ Apostolic Church Ori-Oke Aanun (Mountain of Mercy), Ojoo, Ibadan was a thick and uninhabited forest. But the proprietor of the mountain, Prophet Moses Aladeolu, along with others who worked with him, have, over the years developed the area through different developmental works that opened the environment up to human activities/occupation.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Notes: At the initial stage, the Prayer Mountain was not urbanised because it was situated in a forest area. Subsequent upon the opening up of the area by the praying group, there were a number of reported supernatural occurrences which attracted people to the mountain. Since then, people began to throng the mountain with an attendant result of socio-economic activities, especially of trading in the community. In addition, the Prayer Mountain created and developed a road network that became motorable over the years. This opened up the area to building structures, schools, and a Primary Health Care centre. As a result, a once forested area has now become urbanised and is now connected to the major township of Ojoo in Ibadan.

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: The Christ Apostolic Church Ori-Oke Aanun (Mountain of Mercy), Ojoo, Ibadan is close to the main part of the town. There are motorable roads to the Prayer Mountain that are easily accessible for cars, motorcycles and other vehicles.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Mound

↳ A group of structures:

– No

Notes: The Prayer Mountain structure stands alone as a massive structure but there are other accompanying structures that have been built over the years by the praying group. Some of the other structures that have been built along with the mountainous structure are a worship chapel used for Sunday worship services, 17 chalets for attendees to the Prayer Mountain who intend to stay in an accommodation apart from praying in the open mountains, and an office where the Prophet uses for counselling and prayers.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The Prayer Mountain stands as a single structure of nature but now have other human-made structures such as the chalets, church office, and the worship auditorium.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Other [specify]: For accommodation

Notes: The Prayer Mountain also has rest rooms differently for male and female worshippers who are not booking for accommodation/chalets. There are also places a little distance from the Prayer Mountain that are operated by business owners which serve the basic needs of the praying population on the mountain. These include restaurants and tuckshops where people who are not fasting can eat and buy groceries.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Notes: The prayer mountains are already a finished feature and cannot be improved upon by anyone because they are works of nature.

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: These mountains can even last beyond a generation because they have eternal durability.

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– No

Notes: The Prayer Mountains cannot be modified since they are works of nature and not man-made.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Notes: They are non-destructible elements

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: But the other human accommodation, apart from the Prayer Mountain itself, can be reconstructed or modified due to changing needs or the effect of natural elements on them.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Most of the visitors to Prayer Mountains go there to commune with God, who is a supernatural being in order to get their varied problems resolved

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The Christ Apostolic Church Ori-Oke Aanun (Mountain of Mercy), Ojoo, Ibadan is dedicated to the God described in the Bible

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Notes: The Prayer Mountain is dedicated to the Triune God described in the Bible and not to any other supernatural being. The administrators of the Prayer Mountain only operate the Prayer Mountain as representatives of God.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Notes: It is only God that is worshipped on the Prayer Mountain. The Proprietors of the Prayer Mountain even discourage the adherents to see any of the Pastors/Evangelists on the Prayer Mountain. This is because of the many stories that are heard about some other Prayer Mountains whereby the officiating priests on the mountain turn themselves to demi-gods resulting in ecclesial abuses. But this is not the case on the Christ Apostolic Church Ori-Oke Aanun (Mountain of Mercy), Ojoo, Ibadan.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Notes: The worship of non-divine ancestors is not applicable nor allowed at Prayer Mountains. God is the only divine being being related with/to on Prayer Mountains

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Notes: Prayer Mountains are essentially designated as spiritual centres and acknowledged sacred places. Hence, they are not associated with any official political entity. Even though, the Prayer Mountains are operated by Christians and/ or Christian churches, official political entities do not influence the activities there unlike what can be the case in some designated churches. However, some official political entities do occasionally visit the Prayer Mountains for the resolution of both their personal and political problems.

Reference: Lucy, Lucy. "The Story of the Most Popular Prayer Mountains in Osun State". Ibadan: <https://www.lucipost.com/2019/03/the-story-of-the-most-popular-prayer-mountains-in-osun-state/>, March 5, 2019.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Notes: The Prayer Mountain itself was not constructed by any human because it is the work of nature. But the other accompanying structures such as the Worship auditorium, the chalets, kitchen, and rest rooms were built over the years by the Proprietor of the Christ Apostolic Church Ori-Oke Aanun (Mountain of Mercy), Ojoo, Ibadan, Prophet Moses Aladeolu, and the other Priests along with the visitors to the Prayer Mountain through individual efforts and financial contributions, donations, and tithes of the congregants.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Revealed by high god

Notes: Yes. The Christ Apostolic Church Ori-Oke Aanun (Mountain of Mercy), Ojoo, Ibadan was reported to have been discovered and began by the Prophet Moses Aladeolu through the leading of the Holy Spirit. He was working on a secular job as a government contractor before he received the call of God to begin the Prayer Mountain to be a succor to people's existential and spiritual problems. Hence, the Prayer Mountain began as a result of divine intervention. He even received the exact location of the Prayer Mountain through divine guidance.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Notes: The Prayer Mountains are sacred spaces dedicated to seeking God to resolve their existential problems. They are not to commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being.

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Prophecy

Notes: The founder and proprietor of the Christ Apostolic Church, Ori-Oke Aanun (Mountain of Mercy), Ojoo, Ibadan received an oracular revelation/leading from God to locate the specific location of the Prayer Mountain

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Notes: The structure of the Prayer Mountain itself is the work of nature and not the creation of any external financial donation. But the subsequent attached buildings such as church auditorium, the chalets/accommodations, bathrooms, toilets and shops for the sale of groceries were the contributions of benefactors of the Prayer Mountains over time.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

–Other [specify]: By divine revelation and guidance.

Notes: The Prayer Mountain was established as a result of a supernatural encounter of Prophet Moses Aladeolu with God, and by the need for people to have a place where they can commune with and pray to God and far away from the distractions of noise, television, and phones.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: The Prayer Mountain does not house any Scripture or sacred texts. However, the presiding Prophets or Pastors and the administrators of the Prayer Mountain do interact with the Scriptures (the Bible) and the church hymnals. These are used to exercise their faith in the God they are praying to either individually and or in their congregational prayers.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Notes: The Prayer Mountain, though a work of nature, yet, the operators of the Prayer Mountain have constructed other structures like church auditorium, chalets, church office, bathrooms, toilets,

kiosks/shops, restaurants etc.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the structures on the Prayer Mountain are attached to other rock-like structures on the Prayer Mountain.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

Notes: The prayer mountain itself is made of rocks as it is a mountain. However, the structures built on it are made of materials used locally for building. These include sand, stones, cement, iron rods, nails, roofing steel etc

↳ Sand

– Yes

Notes: Sand is one of the components used in building the structures on the mountain. They are mixed with other materials like cement, stones, iron rods etc.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: It is sourced locally and from the surrounding landscape. They are either gathered around the cite or bought from vendors from nearby.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– No

Notes: Apart from the rocky features of the mountain, clay does not constitute an element for building on the mountain.

↳ Plaster

– Yes

Notes: Plaster is added to other materials used for erecting structures on the mountain. It serves the purpose of gripping other materials together in order to keep the structure together or standing erect.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

Notes: It (cement) for plastering the building is bought from the markets around.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Notes: As a matter of fact, cement for plastering is made from limestone and other materials. However, the cement goes through a manufacturing process. It is therefore not sourced from the Ori-Oke Aanun mountain.

↳ Wood

– Yes

Notes: Though the mountain is made of rocks and not wood, building erected on the mountain have wood as one of their components. The woods are used for beams, roofing members and in other selected places in the buildings.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: The materials are sourced around the mountain and in local markets within the city of Ibadan where the prayer mountain is located.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

Notes: grass does not constitute one of the building elements on the prayer mountain.

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Notes: Stones for the reinforcement of the buildings are bought from vendors in the city.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Not applicable to prayer mountains

Notes: Prayer mountains are natural environments and are not man-made. But those who adopt these mountains do build other physical structures that can support the accommodation of human beings for more than one day though not like the comfort of their homes.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Notes: There are no massive decorations present at/in the Prayer Mountain because they are works of nature. However, there are very simple decorations made of fabrics on the altar and other strategic places on the prayer mountain.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Notes: The Prayer Mountain has no iconography and not even an empty cross is allowed on the Prayer Mountain.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: This is not applicable to the Christ Apostolic Church Ori-Oke Aanun Prayer Mountain

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Notes: The Prayer Mountain is not associated with the worship of the dead. It is a sacred place meant for prayer and fasting and every activity that takes place at the Prayer Mountain involves the living.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Notes: Corpses are not allowed nor treated on the Prayer Mountain. The families of the dead are allowed to treat their dead while the Pastors along with other presiding ministers organise the funeral ceremonies in tandem with the cultural activities. The Prophet Moses Aladeolu only used to attend funeral ceremonies of older church members. In fact, the corpse of a deceased church member is not even allowed inside the church auditorium.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: Grave goods are not allowed in the burial practices of the group.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: There are no cenotaphs on the Prayer Mountain

In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Those who are members of the church wing of the Prayer Mountain, who are not just attendees to the programmes of the Prayer Mountain, are buried in a cemetery or any other place that the family of the deceased chooses.

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

Notes: Members may be buried in family tombs only if the family has such arrangements made.

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– Yes

Notes: The administrators of the Prayer Mountain work in agreement with the family to bury the members of their worshipping community and not the attendees to the Prayer Mountain programmes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: None

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: The God referred to in the Prayer Mountains is divine and not anthropomorphic except that the worshippers at these Prayer Mountains make reference to his being in anthropomorphic terms.

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The Prayer Mountain refers to God in names such as Olorun (the owner of the heaven and who lives in the heavens).

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

Notes: The Christian God, who is sought in the Prayer Mountains, is considered a king and this is why his sovereignty in the affairs of those who throng the Prayer Mountains is largely acknowledged and he is revered and obeyed as espoused by the Pastors who act as God's intermediaries.

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: Not applicable

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: There are testimonies of some of those who visit the Prayer Mountain, especially in their moments of confusion and when they need specific direction in specific areas of their lives. Also, dreams are reported experiences of some visitors at times when they need answers to the questions of the cause of their existential problems. These worshippers can relate to some examples of people whom God communicated with through dreams in the Bible, which is the Scripture of the Christians.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Trance possession has been an occasional reported experience of some worshippers at the Prayer Mountains during individual and congregational prayer meetings. Certain even had reports of angelic visitation.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: The type of divination practice that occurs in the Prayer Mountains in Southwestern

Nigeria is different from that which occurs in the African Traditional Religion or any other non-Christian religion. The Christian ministers who pray for the attendees at the Prayer Mountains do apply counseling with those who still need particular attention even after prayers. There are times that these Pastors or Prophets who are in charge of the Prayer Mountains will give specific instructions to the people through the gift of revelation and seeing visions.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Those who are adherents of the Christ Apostolic Church, Ori-Oke Aanun (Mountain of Mercy), Ojoo, Ibadan have reported having personal encounters with God apart from attending the different specialised prayer programmes organised on the Prayer Mountain. In fact, the proprietor of the Prayer Mountain discourages the attendees from seeing the Pastors and other functionaries. They are encouraged to seek God by themselves.. So, the religious specialists do not act as intermediaries to God even though they may sometimes serve as intervening medium for experiencing divine intervention.

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: None applicable

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Notes: Human spirits do not inhabit the prayer mountain

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– No

Notes: This is not a norm on the Prayer Mountains. However, a few worshippers at the Prayer Mountains have occasionally testified to seeing nonhuman spirits during or after prayers, especially in relation to the resolution of the problems they brought to the Prayer Mountains for God's intervention.

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: This is not the norm on the Prayer Mountains

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: This is not a normal occurrence at the Christ Apostolic Church Ori-Oke Aanun (Mountain of Mercy), Ojoo, Ibadan. But there have been times that certain persons report angelic visitations in their dreams and during prayers on the Prayer Mountain.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Notes: The Prayer Mountains are inhabited by humans who go to seek solutions to their problems through prayer and fasting. They often get some form of assistance from the pastors and prophets who coordinate all spiritual activities on the mountain. There is the presence of the divine who is the God that the worshippers have gone to seek. He is the One whom the religious specialists represent as intermediaries.

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: Communication only occurs between humans and humans and then between humans and God who is the divine being in this human-divine exchange. There is no interaction with any mixed human-divine beings.

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Notes: Cult statue is not an applicable factor to the religious factor of Prayer Mountains

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

Notes: Those who visit the Prayer Mountain are guided by the Pastors and Prophets to know that they are under the watchful eyes of God whom they have come to seek. This is why the worshippers will have to abide by some regulations set up to keep the Prayer Mountain holy and as a spiritual force/channel capable - at all times - of retaining God's presence and making prayers to be answered.

Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Libations:

– No

↳ Offerings of food:

– No

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– No

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:

– No

↳ Daily life objects:

– No

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: Monetary offerings and prayers

Notes: The worshippers at this Prayer Mountain and others in Southwestern Nigeria are encouraged by the religious specialists to give monetary donations in order to fast track the answers to their prayers and also to come and show their appreciation to God after their prayers have been answered.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: The God being prayed to gives them prohibitions relating to sexual relations. In fact, the worshippers must never engage in any form of sexual intercourse on the Prayer Mountain.

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: The worshippers or visitors to this Prayer Mountain are not expected to engage in any

form of sexual activities when on the mountain. Apart from this prayer mountain, there are others in Southwest Nigeria which serve the same purpose. They are expected to observe certain rules as they approach and use the facilities at the Prayer Mountains. For instance, at the Ori-Oke Olorunkole, Akinyele, Ibadan, users are barred from eating any food item, while women are not allowed to climb up the mountain when menstruating. They are equally not allowed to take up any device which connects/interferes with the airwave - (eg) an AM or FM radio device. At the Ori-Oke Ikoyi, Ikoyi, Osun State, visitors to the mountains are not to bring spices (especially local/African pepper) and oil to the mountain. No ladies are allowed on the mountain, and nobody is allowed to miss the general prayer meetings that hold between 10 a.m. and 1 p.m. and between 10 p.m. and 1 a.m. At Ori-Oke Erinmo, Erinmo-Ijesha, Osun State, the worshippers and users of the Prayer Mountain are not to wear any footwears (shoes) on the mountain while eating and drinking are not allowed on the mountain either.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: The rituals that are encouraged and expected on the Prayer Mountain are not the same as that which are required in African Traditional Religion. The rituals are those that concern offering prayers, giving offerings, tithes, and donations, and also prayer and fasting. The worshippers or visitors to this and other Prayer Mountains are expected to observe certain rules as they approach and use the facilities. Some of the rules include; not wearing any form of sandal/shoes on the Prayer Mountains and being physically present at the congregational prayer meetings every Wednesdays and Fridays.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

Notes: Cleanliness and order are the watchword of the religious specialists and the worshippers at the Prayer Mountain because God is revealed in the Scripture as being holy.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: This is evident from the rules and regulations about cleanliness and order that visitors to the Prayer Mountains have to follow strictly or else they will have to be evicted from the Prayer Mountains.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: Visitors to the Prayer Mountains are to keep the vows and pledges they make during their time at the mountain or else they may suffer negative consequences.

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: None applicable

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: The visitors to the Prayer Mountains communicate with God through prayers and fasting

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: The visitors to the Prayer Mountains do not communicate with any other supernatural being.

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Prayers, as a form of Christian rituals, are carried out in the place more than any other form of rituals like giving of offerings.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Rituals like giving money are not done on a large scale because the worshippers are not under any compulsion to give money

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Large and manageable

Notes: The number of participants at any organised programme on the Prayer Mountain is determined by the time of the day and the type of programme being run. There are more people in attendance during monthly and annual programmes than in weekly activities.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Regimented

Notes: The rituals of prayer and giving of financial contributions happen daily

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: Practices are done in accordance with the biblical doctrines agreed upon by the Christ Apostolic Church under the leadership of Pastor S. A. Oladele

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: The practice of prayer are supposedly done in tandem with giving of offerings and fasting

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Notes: Water is the only form of drink allowed on the Prayer Mountain

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: The form of sacrifice acceptable on this and other prayer mountains in southwest Nigeria is that which involves denial of personal comfort and gratification of the flesh. These include fasting for long hours which is not often palatable to the human body, sexual abstinence and withdrawal from all other earthly engagements. These sacrifices are said to assist individuals who engage in them achieve spiritual ascendancy. As they get closer to the supernatural being by consecration, their prayers are said to receive divine attention which results in them achieving their aims of visiting the mountain

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: The forms of self-sacrifices found on this mountain are those just described above. They include fasting for long hours, abstinence from sexual activities etc.

↳ Suicide

– No

↳ Bloodletting

– No

↳ Mutilation

– No

↳ Is self-sacrifice common and/or expect of elites:

– Yes

↳ Is it an elite prerogative:

– No

↳ Is it a kingship prerogative:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

Notes: The visitors to the Prayer Mountains are often encouraged to give material offerings to be a support to get their prayers answered but it is not compulsory and those who are unable to do so are not held in contempt. It is voluntary.

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: There is a difference between valuable objects and the normal gift offerings like offerings and tithes. Visitors to the Prayer Mountain are not compelled to give any valuable objects. Rather every gift is turned into a physical cash. Those who had attempted to give lands and building have been asked to convert them to money

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– No

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Monetary offerings

Notes: The Prophets and Pastors who are in charge of the Prayer Mountains often encourage the visitors to the Prayer Mountains to give money voluntarily to support any ongoing projects relating to the mountain and to give tithes, vows, and pledges to support the administrators of the sacred places.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

Notes: Every visitor to the Prayer Mountain attends the general/corporate prayer. The practice at the ori-Oke Aanun is not different from what takes place at the Ori-Oke Erinmo, Erinmo-ljeshu, Osun State where all visitors to the Prayer Mountain must attend the general prayers everyday between 12 p.m. and 3 p.m. and also every Friday from 12 a.m. to 5 a.m, while at Ori-Oke Ikoyi, Ikoyi, Osun State, general prayers are held every morning from 10 a.m. to 1 p.m. and at night from 10 p.m to 1 a.m.

↳ By specific individuals

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The periodic repairs or reconstructions are not in reference to the mountains on which

the prayers are performed but they are done on the accompanying man-made structures such as church auditoriums, accommodations for the use of visitors according to the need, bathrooms, and toilets.

Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Notes: The maintenance of the Prayer Mountains is often done by visitors to the Prayer Mountains who do it voluntarily and as a way of serving God. Though, the Prayer Mountains do have one or 2 staff, yet, this is not the norm.

Other

– Other [specify]: None applicable

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Notes: But it has been reported that even though the Prayer Mountain does not encourage feasting there, yet, there is feeding during the Prayer Mountain's annual anniversary. Those who come to pray are allowed to go and buy food items at food kiosks below the Prayer Mountain. Then, those who take accommodation in the chalets are allowed to cook food in the kitchen provided.

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

– No

Divination through human communication:

– Yes

↳ Is a human being the vehicle for the oracle:

– Yes

↳ Is a human being the interpreter of the oracle:

– Yes

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: These interpreters are often of the Yoruba ethnic group since the Prayer Mountains under scrutiny are domiciled in the southwestern part of Nigeria

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified class:

– Yes

Notes: The oracle interpreters are Christian ministers and are specifically Pastors and Prophets

↳ Is sex-deprivation required:

– Yes

↳ Are intoxicants required:

– No

↳ Physical ordeal required:

– Yes

Notes: The physical ordeal for the visitors has to do with the rigors of the intense prayer sessions, and fasting which involves denial of food and drinks, and the denial of every other human pleasure.

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:

– No

↳ Divination through non-living material:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: None applies to prayer mountains

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Prayers and gifts of revelation

Notes: The Pastors and Prophets pray and receive oracular revelations for the visitors to the Prayer Mountains who seek for their interventions through the supernatural gifts of revelation, prophecy, and discernment of spirits.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– No

↳ Healing magic

– Yes

Notes: But the healing performed by the Pastors and Prophets through the supernatural intervention of God is not magic but is referred to as a miracle.

↳ Cleansing

– No

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: None applicable

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– No

Notes: The religious specialists of the Prayer Mountain are male and females. The males are referred to as Pastors and Evangelists while the females are referred to as Lady Evangelists. These are given different ecclesial roles according to their spiritual giftings. And they minister along with the Proprietor of the Prayer Mountain, Prophet Moses Aladeolu.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: The religious specialists are largely of the Yoruba ethnic group because the Prayer Mountain is domiciled in the Yorubaland.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

Notes: The religious specialists are ordained Christian ministers or clergymen of the Christ Apostolic Church.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

Notes: The religious specialists are fully dedicated to the Prayer Mountains because they are there as a response to a divine call from God. They can only step out of that assignment if they receive another divine call into another or similar Christian vocation.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Notes: The religious specialists operate within an established hierarchical system of the Christ Apostolic Church.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: But these are not permanent accommodations. The accommodations are provided for the religious specialists as and when they are available to minister on the Prayer Mountain.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The religious specialists undergo informal and formal training on the Christ Apostolic Church Ori-Oke Aanun (Mountain of Mercy), Ojoo, Ibadan. The informal training happens by observing how Prophet Moses Aladeolu and other senior ministers serve on the Prayer Mountain. The formal training takes place through the avenue of the training institute being operated on the Prayer Mountain. This is called Mercy Once Again Bible Institute, where they run Certificate and Diploma certificates in Theology

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The Prayer Mountain has security personnel and cleaners that take care of the place and these are paid monthly salary.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Notes: The existing bureaucracy is permanent rather than temporary.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

Notes: There is food distribution during special programmes which holds in February and December

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

Notes: But they allow government officials to take population census during such exercises.

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– Yes

Notes: The Prayer Mountain has sunk boreholes that are being used by people in the community

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Evangelistic outreaches

Notes: The public services that the Prayer Mountains give to the community are spiritual and not physical. The religious specialists conduct seasonal evangelistic campaigns whereby they engage in preaching about Jesus Christ and pray for people to be healed from their sicknesses and cured of their diseases.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– No

Notes: The only Scripture identified with the Prayer Mountain is the Holy Bible

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

Notes: The founder and proprietor of the Christ Apostolic Church Ori-Oke Aanun (Mountain of Mercy), Ojoo, Ibadan, Prophet Moses Aladeolu established this place, which was a thick forest, by the leading of God with God showing the exact location of the Prayer Mountain in the form of audible voice. There have been many outstanding miracles done on the Prayer Mountain since its establishment.

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: Every religious specialist can interpret the Bible

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible is always found on the Prayer Mountain and in the accompanying accommodations

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– No

Notes: The Bible is not a decoration material but a guide for their life

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible is part of their daily life

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– No

Notes: The Bible is a life guide manual

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: The Bible is a scriptural guide

Notes: The Prayer Mountain allows the Bible to be read and interpreted along with each section of the different programmes because it is used as a guide for every aspect of life.

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